

21st GHRSSST Science Team Meeting

1-5 June 2020, Online

***In situ* SST Quality Monitor (*iQuam*)**

www.star.nesdis.noaa.gov/sod/sst/iquam/

SST Quality Monitor (SQUAM)

www.star.nesdis.noaa.gov/sod/sst/squam/

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NOAA STAR; CSU CIRA; GST Inc.

Supported by JPSS and GOES-R Programs

iQuam v2.1 promoted to main url in Apr 2020

www.star.nesdis.noaa.gov/sod/sst/iquam/

NOAA NESDIS STAR

 iQUAM2 *in situ* SST Quality Monitor v2.10
NOAA / NESDIS / STAR

[Monitor](#) [Data](#) [About](#) www.star.nesdis.noaa.gov/sod/sst/iquam/

Maps
Statistics
Time Series
Platforms

2019 05 28
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 Show hour 0

Month Day

Ref SST used in QC
 Reyn CMC

QCed Outlier

- **Argo** - Argo Floats
- **Drifter** - Conventional drifters
- **HR-Drifter** - High-Resolution Drifters
- **T-Mooring** - Tropical Moorings
- **C-Mooring** - Coastal Moorings
- **CRW** - Coral Reef Watch Buoys
- **Ship** - Conventional ships
- **IMOS** - IMOS Ships

Symbol = one observation.

All Platforms | **Argo** | Drifter | HR-Drifter | T-Mooring | C-Mooring | CRW | Ship | IMOS

Argo Drifter HR-Drifter T-Mooring C-Mooring CRW Ship IMOS iQuam2.2019.05

More iQuam Resources at GHRSSST-XXI: Evaluation of the In Situ SST Quality Control in iQuam, Haifeng Zhang, Poster

Increased number of SST Products Monitored in SQUAM Requires Redesign of the Back End

SST products monitored in SQUAM R2

	Polar L2/L3	Geo L2/L3	Analysis L4
High Res	VIIRS ACSP0 L2P/L3U AVHRR FRAC ACSP0 L2P OSISAF L2P	Himawari-8 AHI ACSP0 L2P/L3U GOES-16 ABI ACSP0 L2P/L3U	MUR (JPL)
Low Res	AVHRR GAC ACSP0 L2P/L3U		CMC (Environment Canada) OSTIA (Met Office) OSTIA RAN (Met Office) GMPE (Met Office) Geo Polar Blended (NOAA) Reynolds (NOAA) GAMSSA (BoM)

• Back End Redesign continues

- Back end was initially designed for much smaller data volumes (e.g., AVHRR only)
- Now processing multiple ACSP0 SSTs (VIIRS/FRAC/GAC/MODIS/ABI/AHI) + external products
- Old back end (combination of IDL + bash scripts) can not keep up
- A more scalable redesign based on python, C++ and SQL database underway
- [Transition of Polar SQUAM complete](#)
- [Geo and L4-SQUAM underway](#)

SST data providers

Satellite missions

